

Coherent & Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for Delivering the EU Green Deal for European Seas

Deliverable 1.5

SPS methodological approach

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AUTHOR(S)	(In alphabetical order) Andrea Barbanti, Emiliano Ramieri, Ginevra Capurso, Folco Soffietti (CNR-ISMAR)
REVIEWED BY	Zeljka Skaricic
APPROVED BY	Froukje Maria Platjouw
PROJECT OFFICER	Gonzalo Garcia de Arboleya
ABSTRACT	The document presents the infographic on the Science-Policy-Society (SPS) methodological approach adopted in CrossGov research and applied in WP2 and WP3 as a component of the coherence and cross-compliance (C&CC) analysis on EU Green Deal policies.
KEYWORDS	EU Green Deal; Science-Policy-Society Interfaces; Policy formulation; Policy implementation.

Introduction

Deliverable 1.5 presents the infographic on Science-Policy-Society (SPS) methodological approach, where the CrossGov methodology for assessing SPSI related to EU marine policies and Green Deal related strategies is presented alongside a selection of key results and examples from case studies, part of the application of the methodology in WP3.

This builds on the application of the methodology presented in Deliverable 1.4 - Guidance document for Science-Policy-Society Interfaces analysis in CrossGov research. Moreover, given that the methodology is and will still be applied, the infographic reports some preliminary outcomes of the analysis, while this will be fully presented in Deliverable 4.3 – Blueprint for SPS.

Content

The infographic is developed in three pages, of which the first one introduces the topic providing relevant definitions of Science-Policy-Society Interfaces and Science-Policy-Society System, the second one presents the methodology referring to Deliverable 1.4 and the third one displays some examples of the results from the analysis applying the methodology carried out by the following case studies in WP3: German North Sea, Oslo Fjord, Mediterranean Sea, French Mediterranean and Northern Adriatic Sea.

Specifically, after the introduction at page one, page two reports and displays in panels the four steps which compose the operational procedure for SPSI analysis as presented in Deliverable 1.4:

- Step 1 - Defining the policy and geographical scope of the analysis and identifying data and information sources;
- Step 2 - Defining the Science Policy Society system under analysis;
- Step 3 - Characterizing the Building Blocks of SPSI to answer the research questions;
- Step 4 - Synthesis: answering the research questions.

Finally, page three presents the five case studies, providing information on the policy, time scale and geographical scope of the analysis and the main data and information sources used in each of them (Step 1 of the methodology). Moreover, textual panels report some main outcomes of the analysis carried out through the Building Blocks part of Step 3, grouped in outputs, methods and inputs, following the classification of the methodology.

Note to the reader

Two versions of the infographic are available below.

The first one is a downloadable pdf, while the second one is a more interactive version, to be possibly uploaded on the website and made accessible online. The main difference is at page three, where in the second version the reader can click on the symbols of each case study to open and read the panels related to the main outcomes of the analysis.

**Coherent & Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for
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Deliverable 1.5: .pdf version

SPS methodological approach

Science Policy Society

Science-Policy-Society Interfaces (SPSI)

are defined as relational undertakings between scientists and other actors in the policy process. They allow for exchanges, co-evolution, and joint construction of knowledge to enrich decision-making.

Science-Policy-Society system

is the set of actors, and connections through which scientific knowledge is acquired, synthesised, translated, presented for use, and applied in the policymaking process.

In this infographic the CrossGov methodology for assessing SPSI related to EU marine policies and Green Deal related strategies is presented alongside a selection of key results and examples from case studies.

Scroll to go the methodology or click on the button to reach the page of interest.

Methodology

Examples

The full deliverable *D1.4 Guidance document for Science-Policy-Society Interfaces analysis in CrossGov research* is accessible on the Cross-Gov website at this [Link](#).

The outcomes of the analysis carried out by applying the methodology will be fully presented in D4.3
Available 31st May 2025

Are you in need of a SPSI Analysis Methodology?

The CrossGov SPS methodological approach is developed to analyse how efficient and effective SPSIs can contribute to sound policy-making and decision-taking, including coherence and cross-compliance of selected and Green Deal-related marine policies.

START

Define the scope of the analysis

The methodology can be applied in a flexible way to different context. For this, an inception phase is needed, to define the scope of the analysis and the following steps.

- The geographical scope of the analysis
- The policies under analysis and which stages of the policy process need consideration
- The time frame of the analysis
- The research questions to be addressed
- The most important sources of information

Define the analyzed Science Policy Society System

By considering the involved actors it is possible to define a system, highlighting who influences who and how.

Characterize the Building Blocks of SPSI to answer the research questions

OUTPUTS

Data & Knowledge
How data and knowledge are made available and used in the policy making and decision making process.

Assessments
How assessments assemble the best knowledge available in a form useful for decision making.

ATTRIBUTES

Availability and access to data; Gaps and uncertainty; Problem framing.

Credibility; Relevance and Legitimacy; Data and knowledge providers; Problem framing.

METHODS

Models and mechanisms
Models of scientific advice and knowledge transfer mechanisms and their effectiveness.

Permanent SPSI platforms
Permanent platforms and their role in SPS and in implementing knowledge transfer mechanisms.

Type of model; Credibility; Relevance and Legitimacy; Type of transfer mechanisms; Utilisation.

Type and role of platforms; Participants; Problem framing.

INPUTS

Competence framework
How competence frameworks and related capacity building activities influence the SPS process.

Funding & resources
How funding, existing infrastructures and resources affect the multiple dimensions of SPSI.

Type of competence; List of competences; Training & capacity building activities and targets.

Type of funding; Drivers for funding; Level and adequacy of funding and resources (including human resources).

Synthesis: answering the research questions

What type of science, knowledge, and interactions do we need for coherent and cross compliant formulation and implementation of policies?

What type of knowledge is currently provided and used in the implementation stages?

Which role does science play in decision-making, policy-mapping and planning?

How is knowledge contributing to horizontal and vertical coherence and cross-compliance of policies?

NEEDS: the science we need

PRACTICES: the science we use

IMPACTS: the impacts of science

EXAMPLES

2004-today

Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) Directive, Renewable Energy Directive (RED) III, biodiversity policies, MSFD, MSPD.

Data for SEA processes is available but varies in accessibility. Difficulties in integrating detailed local and private sector data. Key issues include **knowledge gaps in long-term marine impacts, data standard discrepancies, and partial integration of data into policies** like RED III and MSFD. SEAs for offshore wind energy ensure include evaluation, public participation and integration of multiple policy objectives, evaluating the impacts of wind farms on the marine ecosystem and other maritime activities.

Strategic Environmental Assessments rely on collaborative models involving government agencies, scientific institutions, NGOs, and industry, working together. **SPS platforms contribute that the offshore wind projects comply with national and EU laws**, while providing research and data.

Various capacity-building activities (or planned): **specialized courses in environmental management and offshore technology**, fellowships and internships. The current focus includes a wide range of stakeholders. But there should be an effort in targeting local government officials and community leaders. Funding comes mainly from EU and national funds and by energy companies.

Sources Legend
 ● Desk review – Science
 ● Stakeholder – Society
 ● Government – Policy

* The methodology is still being applied. It will be updated thanks to the listed testers and further case studies that can be accessed on the project's website.

2010-today

Fishery, biodiversity, and climate change policies.

Climate change data are currently not collected in a systematic manner or regulated under a Mediterranean-wide policy framework, although aggregate assessments exist. Fisheries data is generally more influential in different policy frameworks, both the EU-ones (like Marine Strategy Framework Directive and Common Fisheries Policy) and the Mediterranean ones (like Integrated Monitoring and Assessment Programme). Nevertheless, **a large number of fish stocks remains unassessed**. Biodiversity data availability and quality vary among Mediterranean countries. While governance systems struggle to improve data sharing (due to limited funding and enforcement), but broadly there is a lack of action following from the available data.

Scientific policy advice is mostly following a linear model. **Knowledge integration into Med policies is institutionalized through the Barcelona Convention and General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean and Black Seas working groups**, while public involvement is limited to specific projects. **The transfer mechanisms established from delegated experts and national focal points are seen as providing legitimacy** to decisions taken at Mediterranean level, as contracting parties of both Barcelona Convention and GFCM need to be involved. Challenges include funding issues, insufficient engagement and consultation, lack of political will, and non-compliance.

EU funding is the primary source for Med projects, with additional support from national funds, NGOs, and the private sector. **Funding disparities create imbalances**, favoring socio-economic sectors like fisheries over environmental ones. Research priorities often align with available funding.

2019-today

WFD, Municipal spatial plans, Integrated Norwegian Ocean Management Plans (and their effect and interplay of these 3 plans with the sectors agriculture, sewage, fisheries).

The availability of data in decision-making processes is hindered by **limited integration and data-sharing systems across planning and policy processes**, which is further reflected in the fragmentation across multiple portals and databases. This fragmentation is particularly pronounced across jurisdictions along the land-sea interfaces and between environmental and spatial planning policies, creating a significant barrier to effective ecosystem-based management. Example: The monitoring and indicator system of the WFD is mainly tailored to freshwater, falling short of addressing environmental status in the coastal/marine environment. This gap is not filled due to a disconnect from the environmental assessments on the state of the ocean developed as part of the Ocean Management Plan.

Collaborative transfer models prevail. While the implementation of the WFD is characterized by a "network collaboration model," where river basin districts facilitate the integration of decentralized waterbody assessments, the **environmental assessment for ocean management is centralized by the state**. A close integration of science and policy is achieved through a formalized process involving a steering committee (composed of ministries) and two advisory bodies that provide assessments and monitoring data.

Funding mainly comes from the EU (e.g. through projects), the Norwegian government, national authorities and counties along the Oslofjord region.

MSFD, MSPD, WFD, fisheries, renewable energy and biodiversity policies.

2018-today

Abundant data for established directives (WFD, MSPD, Habitat and Bird Directives) but sparse for sectoral policies. Gaps in biodiversity, fish resources, coastal morphodynamics, and climate change impacts. **Assessments for MSFD and WFD are credible and legitimate**. Sectoral policy impact assessments sometimes lack transparency given that funding is provided by private companies.

SPSI model is by tradition linear with a **distinction between science and policy**. Nevertheless, **SPSI platforms exist and involve public institutions** and research centres to support decision-making by sharing data and raising awareness. Collaborative models were recently set up related to the MSPD and the repartition of uses at sea, including stages of public debates and expert consultations. **Sectoral policies such as offshore wind are developed through a stronger collaboration model**.

Capacity-building workshops and other activities related to biodiversity issues have difficulty attracting audiences from other fields. There is a **very strong silo structure between marine environment policies** (WFD, MSFD, MSPD) and **sectoral policies** (fisheries, offshore wind farms) with little collaboration. Funding primarily comes from national schemes and project-led initiatives; some cross-compliant funding exists (e.g. WFD/MSFD). There is a **lack of funding** for operational implementation (human resources) and a mismatch between scientific research timeline (long term) and decision making process (short-term).

2014-today

WFD, MSFD, MSPD, fishery, aquaculture, biodiversity policies.

Data fragmentation and broad access issues in policy implementation. Continuous data sharing systems may be lacking or delayed. **A number of gaps in knowledge areas are present, such as nature-based solutions at the land-sea interface**. Resources limitations (i.e. manpower and skills) in policy assessments. Good examples and successful collaborations are present, e.g. initial MSP assessments. MSPD policy not yet integrated into other policy assessments.

Collaborative transfer models prevail on linear models, but continuity in the knowledge transfer process is still a challenge. **Knowledge production integrated into policy-making**. Researchers act as knowledge brokers in co-design and co-management processes. Societal involvement is limited to consultation. **Permanent SPSI platforms: different focus and levels** (sub-national, national and international). Primarily include administrations, agencies, and research institutions. SPSIs provide technical and scientific support, knowledge transfer, promote engagement and dialogue.

Specialized, sector-specific knowledge can hinder effective collaboration. Workshops and training initiatives, do exist (e.g. EU projects). **Continuity in funding is crucial to ensure stable and adequate human resources**, rather than temporary programs.

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Click on the step's name to uncover it.

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Click on the drawers to access the answers. Roll over the **X** to close them.

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2004-today

German North Sea

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Oslo Fjord

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2014-today

Northern Adriatic Sea

WFD, MSFD, MSPD, fishery, aquaculture, biodiversity policies.

MSFD, MSPD, WFD, fisheries, renewable energy and biodiversity policies.

2018-today

French Mediterranean

MSFD, MSPD, WFD, fisheries, renewable energy and biodiversity policies.

2010-today

Mediterranean Sea

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